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NOD2 NACHT mutation results in nuclear transport defects.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

Features included Lamin A/C activation, failure to induce expression of the RanGEF RCC1 and nuclear pore complex component NUP210, together with activation of export pathway machinery CRM1/XPO1, and the import receptors karyopherin alpha 1 and importin 13.